

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT STRATEGY AND SELECTION ISSUES

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Abstract: The article analytically examines the ideas on the strategy of human resource management.

Keyword: human resources, personnel management, market economy

Our country, becoming equal in the world community from year to year, boldly follows the path of development we have chosen to its main goal – the formation and development of a democratic rule of law and civil society based on a socially oriented market economy in which human interests, rights and freedoms are the highest value. The growth of incomes of the population, a significant increase in living standards as a result of increased proportionality between various spheres and sectors of the economy and ensuring sustainable growth rates create the basis for strengthening confidence in tomorrow.

Achieving the formation of educated and enterprising personnel for the development of the country's economy is of great socio-economic importance in the implementation of economic reforms of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Currently, Personnel management in our country is one of the urgent problems. In this direction, the Government of our country has adopted a number of regulatory legislative acts. As an example, the law "On Education", the national training program, the Presidential Decree "On improving the system of advanced training and exchange of experience of promising young pedagogical and scientific personnel" can be cited. In addition to the technical and technological renewal of production enterprises, the existing personnel management system and personnel management require further improvement. This is becoming an even more urgent problem in the modern market economy. The level of development of society is largely determined by the size and composition of the population existing in the country. The active part of the country's population invests their strength, knowledge and qualifications in work, production, and provision of services. The active part of the population consists of able-bodied and able-bodied population. The period of working capacity is understood as the period preceding the established age of a person, and by working capacity is a sufficient level of his mental and physical abilities. Thus, the active part of the population is called human resources.

Human resources are people, their work ethic and desire to achieve their goals, their system of knowledge and values, their creative and innovative abilities. These same factors contribute to economic growth, well-being and security in the country. A decisive role is played by profound transformations in the sphere of labor, employment conditions and the system of labor relations, without which a real turn towards man as the main goal of a socially oriented economy cannot be realized. However, it should not be concluded from the above that this concept is unsuitable for a market economy. On the contrary, the development of a market economy shows that human resources are increasingly immersed in the system of market categories. Human resources are not only labor resources, they can be specified in other categories, such as economically active and inactive population, employed and unemployed population, labor force, personnel. In the effective provision of the activities of

modern enterprises, along with the means of labor, human resources – personnel - are also important. It is the employees who manage the production, carry out current and long-term planning and ensure the use of production.

The higher the professional qualifications of the personnel, the better the economic and production indicators of the enterprise. Today, during the period of deep-rooted market economy in our country, in accordance with the "national training program", a number of new requirements are being put forward. Among them, the most significant are: socio-psychological management, analysis and regulation of interpersonal relationships in groups, managerial relationships, management of industrial and social conflicts and stress, information support of the personnel management system, employment management, evaluation of candidates for vacant (vacant) positions and analysis of personnel needs, personnel marketing, career planning and issues of labor relations, labor ergonomics and labor aesthetics. The changes taking place in the economic and political systems of our republic, along with great opportunities for each person, the stability of his life, carry serious risks, practically introducing a certain degree of uncertainty into the life of each person. Personnel management in this situation is of particular importance, as it allows you to implement the whole range of issues of human adaptation to external conditions, taking into account the personal factor in the structure of the personnel management system in the organization. Therefore, it will be necessary to develop completely new approaches to the priority of spirituality and values. The main aspect inside the enterprise and the organization is the staff, and outside the organization – the consumers of products. It is necessary to turn the spiritual consciousness of the performer to face the initiator, and not to the boss. Generalization of the experience of organizations in Uzbekistan and abroad allows us to formulate the main goal of the personnel management system, namely the provision of personnel, their effective functioning, professional and social development. In accordance with this, the personnel management system of the enterprise and the organization is formed.

Uzbekistan is working to support and stimulate the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, services and home work, further development of industrial and social infrastructure as the most important areas for further improving employment and improving the welfare of the population. Stages of human resource management in large organizations, responsibility for the overall management of human resources is assigned to qualified employees of the human resources department, which is usually part of the staff services. In order for these specialists to help in the implementation of the goals of the organization, they need to know not only their field of activity, but also the needs of subordinate managers. At the same time, these managers cannot fully use the services of human resources specialists if they do not understand the specifics of human resources management, its mechanism, capabilities and shortcomings. Therefore, it is important that all leaders know and understand the methods and methods of managing people.

The human resource management system includes the following stages:

1. Resource planning: development of a plan to meet future human resource needs.
2. Recruitment: organization of a reserve of potential candidates for all positions.
3. Selection: evaluation of job candidates and selection of the best from the reserve.
4. Determination of wages and benefits: development of the structure of wages and benefits in order to attract, hire and retain employees.

5. Career guidance and adaptation: familiarization of employees with the organization and its divisions, formation of an employee's idea of what is expected of him, an explanation of what work is well evaluated.

6. Training: development of training programs for the necessary labor skills for effective performance of work.

7. Evaluation of labor activity development of a methodology for evaluating labor activity and bringing it to the employee.

8. Promotion, demotion, transfer, dismissal: development of methods for transferring employees to positions or other areas of work.

9. Management of training, maintenance of management personnel: development of programs aimed at improving labor efficiency and developing the abilities of management personnel.

The content of the concept of "personnel" ("human resources"). The term "personnel" unites the components of the company's workforce. The personnel includes all employees who perform production or management operations and are engaged in processing with the use of labor items, labor tools. At the same time, the concepts of "staff", "employees", "staff" mean the same thing. In management theories, there are various approaches to the classification of personnel based on the profession and career of an employee, the level of management, categories of employee. Depending on the participation in the production process, the staff is divided into two main parts: workers and employees.

In foreign practice, there are two main approaches to solving personnel problems. The first approach focuses on the fact that "human resource management" includes strategic aspects of solving this problem, as well as social development issues, and they are given priority attention. And the concept of "personnel management" implies faster work with personnel. If the first approach proceeds from the tasks of employment and its coordination at the state level, then the second - directly from the labor relations at the enterprise level and their coordination. The different meanings of expressions are related to the nature and focus of the activity. Thus, the phrase "employee" in most cases is applied to small enterprises (with fewer than 100 employees), and the phrase "human resources" - to large enterprises with more than 2.5 thousand employees. Personnel management is a system of interrelated organizational, economic and social measures for the normal development, functioning and effective use of the potential of the workforce at the enterprise, firm level.

Personnel management appears as a continuous process that expresses the reasons why employees work, receive a high degree of profit from it, and hence the final high results in the activities of enterprises. In functional terms, personnel management refers to all tasks and solutions related to work in the personnel sphere, for example, recruitment, use of personnel, their professional development, remuneration, dismissal, etc. In organizational terms, this concept refers to all persons and institutions responsible for working with personnel, for example, managers, personnel department, production councils, trade unions. In our opinion, human resource management consists in the fact that people are the competitive wealth of the enterprise, they need to be placed, developed, justified along with other resources, the purpose of which is to achieve the strategic goals of the enterprise. The concept of "enterprise personnel" in a fairly general form covers all employees of this enterprise and organization performing absolutely specific tasks. In the period of

transition to a market economy, human resource management is gaining new importance. Human resource management has its own characteristics and consists of several stages. Managers of enterprises and organizations need to take into account these features for effective operation. An important conclusion for human resource management is that transferable management practice should be considered not as a set of simple, technical indicators, but as a set of socio-technical parameters. Many Western companies (as well as Scientists) superficially study Japanese methods of work and think that they can be easily applied in other countries. They often deny the socio-cultural foundations that are less noticeable in this complex.

